

FREQUENCY OF SUDDEN CORONARY DEATH IN HEART AND LUNG DISEASES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199508>

Annotation: 279 patients who applied with the diagnosis of ischemic heart disease, unstable tension angina, and ventricular fibrillation were taken as the material of the scientific research in the emergency cardiology department of the Khorezm regional branch of the Republican Emergency Medical Research Center. Sudden coronary death is the most common death in people with chronic cardiovascular and respiratory diseases.

Keywords: Sudden coronary death, ischemic heart disease, unstable angina pectoris, ventricular fibrillation, pulse, unstable angina, myocardial infarction in the first hours, previous myocardial infarction, chronic heart failure, cardiomegaly, Brugada syndrome

Research material and methods: 279 patients who applied with the diagnosis of ischemic heart disease, unstable angina pectoris and ventricular fibrillation were taken as the material of the scientific research in the period from 18.08.2022 to 27.05.2023 in the emergency cardiology department of the Khorezm regional branch of the Republican Emergency Medical Research Center. The ageing index of the patients was between 44 and 81 years old in men, their average age index was 69.25 years, and in women, it was between 49 and 76 years old, and the average age index was 65.78186 patients (66.66%) were men, 93 patients (33.34%) were women. The diagnosis was made on the basis of the patient's complaint, medical anamnesis, objective examination, as well as paraclinical data. Sudden coronary death is the most common death in people with chronic cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Sudden fainting occurs within an hour after the onset of acute symptoms of the disease. In such cases, the presence of cardiovascular or respiratory diseases in the patient may be clear or unclear, but death is always happens unexpectedly.

The World Health Organization considers sudden coronary death to be a witnessed death occurring within an average of 1 to 6 hours after the onset of the initial heart attack. One of the main causes of sudden coronary death is ventricular fibrillation. According to the sudden coronary death, i.e. primary cardiac arrest (Table 1) of the patients who came to complain, we conditionally divided the patients into two groups according to the frequency of meetings according to their gender and age. The first group consisted of patients between the ages of 44 and 64 years, with a 7-fold higher incidence among men than women, and the second group included patients between the ages of 65 and 85 years, with a 2:1 male-to-female ratio of sudden coronary death.

Clinical signs of the onset of sudden coronary death.

1. Dizziness and weakness (76-98%)
2. Sudden loss of consciousness (70.2-96.8%)

3. Undetectable pulse in large arteries (68.3-91.2%)
4. Cardiac arrest (64.9-83.7%)
5. Respiratory arrest or agonal breathing (61.4-79.2%)
6. Changes in skin color (60.7-79.0%)
7. Convulsions or a single tonic contraction of body muscles were observed in patients (58.3-72.4%).

1-table

Primary cardiac arrest was observed in the early morning and the first half of the day. When the patients came with a complaint, there were no signs that could be used to make a diagnosis other than ischemic heart disease. More sudden coronary death occurs in unstable angina, in the first hours of myocardial infarction, in patients with previous myocardial infarction and chronic heart failure and cardiomegaly, as well as in severe arrhythmias, Brugada syndrome and several Occurs in people with XO. Brugada syndrome belongs to the group of autosomal-dominant hereditary diseases and is characterized by polymorphic ventricular tachycardia leading to sudden death. At the age of 35-45, arrhythmia occurs during sleep, syncope and sudden death. In this syndrome, ventricular fibrillation occurs under the influence of the vagus nerve, and ECG shows syncope during the right bundle branch block, S-T interval prolongation in V1-V3 branches, and polymorphic ventricular tachycardia. Signs of true biological death in sudden coronary death:

Keratinization of the corneal paranoid

- Dilation of the pupils and lack of exposure to light
- Immobility of the chest
- Bruising of the skin and mucous membranes
- Muscle stiffness
- Appearance of palm-sized spots

Conclusion: 279 patients who applied with the diagnosis of ischemic heart disease, unstable angina pectoris and ventricular fibrillation were taken as the material of the scientific research in the period from 18.08.2022 to 27.05.2023 in the emergency cardiology

department of the Khorezm regional branch of the Republican Emergency Medical Research Center. The age index of the patients was between 44 and 81 years old in men, their average age index was 69.25 years, and in women, it was between 49 and 76 years old, and the average age index was 65.78. 186 patients (66.66%) were men and 93 patients (33.34%) were women. The diagnosis was made on the basis of the patient's complaint, medical anamnesis, objective examination, as well as paraclinical data. Primary cardiac arrest was observed in the early morning and in the first half of the day. When the patients came with a complaint, there were no signs that could be used to make a diagnosis other than ischemic heart disease. According to the sudden coronary death, i.e. primary cardiac arrest (Table 1) of the patients who came to complain, we conditionally divided the patients into two groups according to the frequency of meetings according to their gender and age. The first group consisted of patients between the ages of 44 and 64 years, with a 7-fold higher incidence among men than women, and the second group included patients between the ages of 65 and 85 years, with a 2:1 male-to-female ratio of sudden coronary death.

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